

The Digital Transformation: Key Attributes and Challenges

S. Sagayarajan¹, Dr. A. Shaji George²

Shine University, India^{1,2}

E-mail: ¹ssagay@yahoo.com; ²drashajigeorge@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

As a catalyst for positive and radical change, digital transformation represents a complex issue that affects people from all walks of life and the whole economy. The objective and ultimate aim of this procedure are efficient business processes as well as operations through rigorous use of ICT. The study topic of this research paper is the key attributes and challenges of the digital transformation process of business in both the private and public sectors. This paper analysis shows that some aspects, like the pace of transformation, the culture and working environment, viewpoint are substantially underdeveloped. More precisely this document is intended to place the current knowledge about the subject in order. We introduce a systematic analysis of scientific and technical literature regarding how digital transformation facilitates business, we demonstrate that the knowledge regarding how digital transformation assists in the business. Moreover, key attributes and challenges within this topic are emphasized. Furthermore, the research paper provides the roadmap for digital transformation.

Keywords: Digital Transformation, Key attributes, Digital Transformation Challenges, Business, Public and Private Sectors, Common Goals, Digital Transformation Process.

1.INTRODUCTION

The Digital transformation is the great transformation of business and managerial activities, methods, skills, and models to completely leverage the modifications and possibilities of a blend of digital technologies as well as their hastening impact throughout society in the strategic and arranged way, with the current and future shifts into consideration. With the emergence of innovative digital technologies, companies in nearly every industry domain are performing multiple programs to discover and take advantage of their benefits [12,13]. This often includes transformations of important business activities and has an impact on products and procedures, and administrative structures, as companies have to establish business administration practices to control these sophisticated transformations [14]. Digital transformation will affect all segments of society, specifically economies. Firms now are given the chance to drastically change their business models through new digital technologies. This mainly involves modifications to the core of the company's business activities and alters products and procedures, and organizational structures, as businesses should

establish administration practices to carry out these sophisticated transformations [18]. Thus, the community as a whole is confronting a quick and radical shift owing to the maturation of digital technologies as well as their universal penetration of the entire market [15]. Adding to the heightened demand from clients, firms are facing ever stronger competition because of globalization [16] as well as placing pressure to become digital before the others do, pursuing to persist and achieve competitive benefits[17]. Digital transformation is an integration of digital technologies into all sectors of a business, radically changing the way that one operates and delivers value to clients. It is also a cultural change that requires organizations to constantly challenge the current situation, research, and become accustomed to failure. Though businesses that long controlled their own industries discovered their traditional value proposition under danger [18]. Nevertheless, in spite of the variety of technological innovations as well as formulas for their application, whether in the business, community management, and private life, real Digital Transformation is taking significantly longer and is faced with more obstacles than it has been anticipated [19]. Effective Digital Transformation involves a particular organization expanding a wide variety of abilities, which will differ in significance depending upon the business environment and the particular organization's requirements. Digital technology wishes to become a key element in how the company works, and organizations successfully must evaluate and potentially re-develop their own business models in order to stay competitive [20]. This research paper offers an introduction about how digital services, as well as applications, are to be shaped and provided to stimulate this transformation. And it also reviews the opportunities and challenges of digital transformation and common goals to achieve the transformation. In conclusion, in this research paper the following concepts are explained: the digital transformation, transformation process, and how to construct working environments that enable rapid and high-quality decisions. The following article reviews and firmly concentrates on the idea of Digital Transformation, its key attributes, and its Challenges.

2.METHODOLOGY

In this study, the researcher pursues a deductive method in which the justifications, as well as arguments, are backed by practical facts and related theories. The researcher has been reviewed by academic journal articles, industry publications as well as the report from the institutions like research centers, technology advisory, and strategy consulting services, and the report from reliable websites to understand Digital transformation and the key attributes and challenges of digital transformation. The paper also examines the opportunities and challenges of digital transformation as well as common goals to achieve it. Throughout this research paper, the following concepts are explained: the digital transformation, the transformation process, and how to create a working environment that allows for rapid, high-quality decision-making. The following article reviews and firmly concentrates on the idea of Digital Transformation, its key attributes, and its Challenges. Document format is that of a concept

paper, while arguments have empirical support. In Conclusion, the researcher examines and concludes the paper proposing future exploration paths in accordance with the combined discussions.

3.OVERVIEW OF THE DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

Digitalization is the integration of technology into all areas of business. A completely new approach to business and corporate processes, corporate culture, and customer service. In the field of corporate culture, digital transformation needs constant questioning, dissatisfaction, experimentation, and creative thinking. The goal is to transform traditional businesses into digital ones. It can be challenging to enumerate one definition of digital transformation that applies to all businesses due to the fact that it is different for every organization. To put it simply, this means moving away from long-term business processes that were formerly applied to businesses, and focusing on evolving, continuously defined processes [11].

4.DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION PROCESS

Digitization

The word Digitization has come about in 2015 to specify a procedure of great transformation of a business to digital technology, changing a business model and the stream of value. Digitization involves a deep structural and strategic transformation to the business, like giving up the physical infrastructure in order to act upon an online platform. The phrase also includes all the process of incorporating value chains of products and services in real-time through means of digital platforms and, in conclusion, can be regarded as the highest possible use of the accessible technological possibilities, in an integrated approach.

Digitalization

Digitalization is a transformation of any kind of physical representation into digital form. It typically involves some kind of capturing tool and it is used to reduce the paperwork of operations and optimize methods. It represents the first stage in the process of evolution, and it does not require the need to completely remove the physical object. When someone tells the business process was digitalized, that means it has disappeared from a state of what it means to be 100% paper-dependent towards a model where documentation will be stored and processed digitally.

Digital Transformation

It is the convergence of the digital approach as an entire, including the operational, tactical, and management areas. The company discovers itself in the phase of adaptive Innovation as well as digital thinking pervades all the decision-making in the enterprise. Throughout the operational sector, some notice the usage and the integration of digital technological tools, a transformation of processes, as well as the digitalization of documents, the transformation to cloud data processing, and the optimization of the methods usually. In a strategic sector, there is a profoundly significant change in the path to work, concentrating more on the requirements of a consumer to do more forceful choices and create solutions of value. As well as in the managerial facet, one sums up the development of the company's business model, which captures the business opportunities that are generated through the adaptation of the digital.

Fig. 1 Digital Transformation Process

5.THE OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

Digital transformation offers organizations with both a significant challenge and an opportunity[3]. When you plan for the digital transformation organizations need to take into account the cultural changes they will face as workers and organizational managers adapt to the adoption and the reliance on different technologies[4]. Digital transformation has generated distinctive marketplace challenges as well as opportunities [5] such organizations have to contend with agile competitors that take advantage of the low obstacle to entry that the technology provides[6]. Furthermore, owing to the high importance provided today to the technology and the extensive use it the consequences of digitalization for-profits revenues as well as opportunities possess a remarkable positive potential[7].

6.CHALLENGES IN THE FIELD OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

There have been a few problems that nearly all of the organizations in the business decided were the biggest challenges on the way to digitalization. It is simple to duplicate the technology, organizational structure, as well as the workflow of digital indigenous companies on paper. It may look as straightforward as upgrading a software release, although it is not. This technology may be simple, but individuals are not. [1] On the individual side of digital transformation, the biggest challenge is the understanding that digital transformation involves leadership in managing change. It is not a matter of an investment in certain software after which it is done. Modern software development tools and procedures enable innovative workflows that organizations require time to adapt to and adjust. Digital transformation involves gradual and permanent modifications to the way people are working. The greatest technical challenges of digital transformation are more likely to be a particular combination of implementing new technologies, utilizing data science as the driver for business enhancement, and the difficulties with legacy systems. Legacy systems that do not communicate with each other and share information, and frequently containing distorted data, could create real barriers. [2] Difficulties with legacy systems could slow processes down instead of speeding them up. With No transparency into the application release methods which deliver client value, a business enterprise has not been able to efficiently manage its digital transformation challenges.

7.COMMON GOALS OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

In any digital transformation, setting objectives is the most important step. The setting of objectives provides employees with a clear focus on where they should focus their efforts[9]. Giving team targets, motivates them to work toward them. Furthermore, objectives help evaluate, track and measure the project's performance as well as employee satisfaction[10].

The following are common goals that digital transformation can accomplish to guide in the right direction when transforming the company.

COMMON GOALS OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

Fig. 2 Common Goals of Digital Transformation

8.FACTORS FOR SUCCESS OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

The digital transformation is even more of an advancement than a transformation, a successful transformation is one that follows the step-by-step method of applying the most appropriate solutions for the present state of organizations. A Digital Transformation(DT) Model will be based on five of the most significant operational drivers of a digital transformation process[2]. Presenting excellence in those five areas of the organization offers an excellent basis for the achievement of every digital transformation.

Fig. 3 Success factors for digital transformation

Leadership and culture

The kind of leadership and culture required for a very successful digital transformation could be described as similar to that of a successful team, one where people will be given the space and the chance to do the best they can.

Employee involvement

The organization could push digital excellence by ensuring that employees are fully involved in the process.

Value-chain, partners, and trends

Possessing an in-depth understanding of whatever the digital developments are in the business and working together with partners and vendors who are the best in class enables an organization to concentrate on changing those practices that are most crucial to the success of the enterprise.

Emerging technologies

The key to digital transformation is the ability to execute and make the best use of both new and emerging technologies available at the moment to enhance business operations and performance.

Business intelligence and data science

Since, automation and digitization start to create valuable information about processes, clients, and services, using the information to notify and guide decisions is the next phase in a process of constant improvement.

9.HOW DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION DRIVES SUCCESS

Notwithstanding the differences in businesses, starting points, as well as goals, executive teams struggle with extremely similar queries at the beginning of a transformation[8].

Why is this done? Do businesses want to become much more receptive to quickly changing customer requirements? Does the productivity of businesses require a step transformation improvement? Is the business's capacity to innovate trailing?

What should be done? The extent of digital transformations differs broadly, from concentrating on people to revamping technology as well as infrastructure, replacing legacy IT platforms, as well as moving to the cloud. Many businesses concentrate on specific business results, for example in customization and digital marketing, end-to-end client journeys, as well as digital supply chains, and the digital common services[8].

How do businesses execute the transformation? There are several questions over leadership, resource allocation, administration, emphasis, methodology, and sequence analysis. How can we be certain that the product, networks, as well as support functions work in harmony with the technology function, and how business can get middle managers on the project?

Executives should make many significant decisions prior to the beginning, and there are typically (reasonably) differing opinions throughout the leadership table[8]. These can vary from encouraging cooperation, fostering integration amongst employees, creating opportunities for changing the mindset of employees, testing pilots before expanding to other areas, and committing the whole organization to change.

10.THE ATTRIBUTES OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

In evaluating the fast-evolving world of digitalization, several defining attributes of digital transformation have emerged[21].

A Hyper-attention to the customer experience. Organization typically starts digital transformation through developing a full understanding of the client. Customer Information, what are the demographics of the clients, how does the company interact with its customers, constantly enhancing the client experience is considered to be the “make or break” aspect for digital transformation[21].

Well-defined operational processes, efficient, and more transparent. For digital transformation to be successful, operational processes must be well-defined. A process like this not only produces the data the organization needs for decision making, but it also makes the organization more responsive to both inside and outside customer demands and facilitates good knowledge transfer within the organization[21].

Transparent integration between data and process. At The Same Time, it must be the situation in any organization, through the digital transformed organization, the decisions are taken based upon the facts the data generated from processes. Moreover, data is used to modify the way the company works. And utilize data obtained to make course adjustments or additional tactical decisions[21].

Focus on Value, not Activities. Digital transformation is not merely an enhanced e-commerce system but is an entirely new way of thought about how an enterprise provides value by an ecosystem of events. Digital transformation results in a culture that questions the current situation and aggressively seeks the possibilities to provide value in the new, innovative approach maybe even leading to new commercial models [21].

11.CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

Digital transformation has achieved an enormous interest by corporate sector experts and academics at present because of its innovative influence of advanced digital technologies on providing exceptional involvement with customers or discovering the means by which the companies take advantage of effective processes. Furthermore, with the emergence of new technologies as well as dynamic markets and clients, all businesses are taking initiative to take advantage of and find out more technical benefits via business model innovation, restructuring of product, procedures, and organizational structures, etc., Whenever it comes to digital transformation, there is absolutely no make-or-break point. Digital transformation is a process that slowly brings organizations through different stages of technological innovations and enables them to become quicker and more aggressive in the present market.

Additionally, digital transformation is an integrated and comprehensive process that encompasses a certain number of procedures, interactions, changes in technology, and internal as well as external influences. This continuing journey wants to be backed by the right leadership and the people, not only the right technology. Though, by analyzing all the relevant definitions, features, viewpoints, dimensions as well as models debated in the expanding body of research it can be used to identify that a company wants to concentrate on its digital approach roadmap, which represents the go-to-market, commitment, business activities, and organization factors. A company will have to be concentrated and address may be used as a foundation through the process of creating requirements, gap identification, and formulation of the digital transformation process. Example Offering,

Networks, Clients, Associates, Workforce, Procedures, IT Expertise, Structure, Motivation, and Culture. Digital transformation is an extremely dynamic and appropriate aspect that organizations require to focus on in their policy design process. Digital transformation is not only about disruption or technology. It is about people, value, optimization, and the ability to quickly adjust when adaptation is required via the smart use of technologies as well as information. With our assessment, we hope to offer a thorough and solid basis for the present discussions on digital transformation and to encourage future studies on this fascinating topic.

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